

The War

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The inevitable War is a historic and actual preoccupation that will never end. Thought time many famous writers described the concept till our days about nuclear War.

I reproduce a selection of Authors and texts for a reflection on this issue.

John Locke's thought:

"The state of War is a state of enmity and destruction.

Being reasonable and just, may I have the right to destroy what threatens to kill me, for, by the fundamental law of nature, the man should be preserved as much as possible when all cannot be kept, security should be preferred.

And a man who comes to make War can be destroyed or an enemy found in our existence, for the same reason that a wolf or a lion can be killed because such men are not subject to the common law of cause; it is the rule other than force and violence.

It can thus be treated as ferocious animals, dangerous and harmful creatures that will surely destroy us whenever we fall into their hands. "

Conceptualizing War, says **Clausewitz**:

"War is an act of violence designed to force the enemy to submit to our will."

This thought of the Prussian military thinker expresses, thoroughly and transparently, the War lived and studied by Clausewitz, a contemporary one of the so-called Wars of Revolution and Napoleonic Campaigns.

The Clausewitz concept has become the paradigm of Western thinking about War. It has dominated the spirit of the German, French, and Russian authors during this century and a half that separates us today from the first edition of Vom Kriege.

Sun Tzu's classic work rests on a passage that reveals the key to his philosophy. Says the Chinese author:

"War is a grave concern for the state; it needs to be thoroughly studied."

For the first time, the eastern writer characterizes the constancy of War in the life of states, stating:

"Armed struggle is not an ephemeral anomaly, but a conscious act that must, therefore, be rationally analyzed."

Penetrating the theme that characterizes the essence of his theory of War, the predominance of intelligence over brutality, skill over the shock, and psychological subversion of the adversary's mind over the bloody battle, thus manifests the Chinese general and philosopher:

"The general who is considered master in the art of conquest must know how to thwart his enemy's plans, compromising his alliances, creating disagreements between the sovereign and his ministers, between the superiors and inferiors, between the chiefs and subordinates. Its agents must be everywhere, gathering information, sowing discord, and inciting subversion.

The enemy must be isolated and demoralized; you will fight till resistance, broken.

Thus, the enemy will fall without combat, his army will be conquered, his cities occupied, and his government replaced. Only when it is not possible to defeat the enemy by these means should the armed force be resorted to, and thus, as follows:

- for a shorter period;
- with the least sacrifice of human lives;
- inflicting on the enemy the smallest possible material losses.

Says Sun Tzu: - "the good strategist who is capable of defeating the enemy without attacking him, of occupying the enemy cities without destroying his assets, of occupying their territory without the need for bloody shocks."

Still conceptualizing War, Clausewitz points out that it is "an instrument of national politics."

Raymond Aron finds three main components in strategic theory: knowledge supported by natural science, conceptual idea, obedience to principles valid in most cases. Translating into military language, we would say geographical knowledge of the area of operations and the means, the concept of purpose, and application of the general principles of War (information, security, command unit, articulation of the media, etc.).

For **André Glucksmann**, the concept of War imposes a strategic calculation. So we see the strategy-calculation of how to make War. At the bottom, we fall, as we shall see later, into the same essential thing, though the language of the philosopher and the military strategist is different.

In short, we are faced with two clear philosophies about War:

- That of submission by the use of brute force (polarized in Clausewitz's ideas), and

- The submission of mind control (presented by Sun Tzu).

In both, the same end is sought - military defeat - and consequently political dominance.

In the war scenario that presents itself today and glimpses into the future, one perceives, permeated by modern strategic conceptions, these two philosophical conceptions of War.

"War no longer belongs to the realm of the arts or sciences but is related to social existence. It is a conflict between major interests decided by the bloodshed. It looks more like politics."

From these thoughts of Clausewitz, who lived a few years in Imperial Russia, where he held a Professor's chair in Political Science and Strategy, Lenin extracted his concept of permanent War.

Paraphrasing Clausewitz, **Lenin** wrote his famous phrase that "Politics is the continuation of war by other means."

As Clausewitz himself had predicted, in the future, there would be, in addition to military Strategy, strategies corresponding to the fields of generalization - of war-political, economic, social, and others.

In modern military thinking, three leading schools predominate over the Strategy:

- Direct action strategy;
- Indirect action strategy,
- Deterrence strategy.

Each of these schools has its leading thinker. Clausewitz is the proponent of the first, Liddell Hart of the second and General Beaufre of the third.

According to Karl von Clausewitz, in his classic book *Of War*, "the political objective of war is to destroy the enemy's military forces and conquer their territory."

As a military strategy to achieve this political objective, the German writer prescribes - "to fight the battle, there is no other way."

As strategic principles of Clausewitz's thought, they found: "To concentrate forces and launch them against the enemy's central mass, to reach the decision for battle, if possible in one action and at a single moment. It is the so-called Action Strategy.

Against the enemy's main forces (it's center of gravity), realizing, if possible, strategic surprise.

When studying Napoleon's campaigns, Clausewitz selects as factors of strategic :

- Surprise:
- Mobility;
- Speed;
- Diversionary actions, and
- disclosure.

False information aimed at deceiving the enemy on the point of application of the decisive blow.

Liddell Hart, in his book on Strategy, published in 1954, contradicts Clausewitz's thinking and proposes as a new strategy, indirect action, which can be translated as follows:

"The most useful Strategy is one that allows the battle to be conducted most advantageously, and many of these advantageous conditions, if applied, could lead to the imbalance of enemy forces with a minimum of combat.

In short, the perfect Strategy will be to make the decision for the defeat of the enemy and his surrender without a battle. "

In one of his books in 1937, Mao Zedong said: "The first law of war is to preserve our forces and destroy the forces of the enemy."

According to General Beaufre, a brilliant synthesizer of Total War Strategy of our time, "Strategy is the art of the dialectic of wills, using force to resolve its conflicts. It is the will of men, the will of peoples, and even today, it is necessary that they want to fight and win. "

But General Beaufre, in his Total War Strategy, does not focus solely on the aspects of nuclear conflict. He writes:

"Nuclear deterrence, paralyzing the war conflict, leaves a very narrow margin of freedom of strategic action: that which is exploited by the Soviet Strategy on the world community.

Political and economic action, the use of revolutionary movements, and even local conflicts seeking to escape the paralysis imposed by nuclear deterrence. "

"Military strategy is the art of using the battle to achieve the objectives of the war."
(Clausewitz, Vom Kriege.)

"Military strategy is the art of distinguishing and applying military means to achieve the goal of war." (Liddell Hart, Strategy.)

General Beaufre observes that:

"Strategy is not the Technique, nor the Tactics, let alone the Logistics and even the Politics, but the intermediate level between the high Politics and the Tactics; the gear that allows us to order the use of force to achieve better the ends set by the excellent Policy. "

Four centuries ago, **Machiavelli** advised: "As regards the exercise of the mind, the Prince must read history and consider the action of the great men, see how they conducted themselves in wars, examining the causes of their victories and defeats, to escape these and imitate those. "

The synthesis of Clausewitz's political thinking about War can be summed up in his famous phrase - "War is the continuation of politics by other means."

Studying Clausewitz, Soviet revolutionary leader Lenin decided to use the Prussian writer's phrase and give him a new revolutionary version, saying, "Politics is the continuation of war by other means." In this inversion, Lenin derives from Marxist doctrine the philosophical-sociological concept of permanent revolution, permanent struggle, and, by approximation, permanent War.

For General Beaufre (Introduction a la Stràtegic), the Indirect Action Strategy today represents a warlike diversion that replaces total War, made impractical since the appearance of the nuclear weapon. The same author says that "the indirect action strategy is the complement and, in a way, the antidote of the nuclear strategy."

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Paraphrasing Sun Zu:

- "Only when all the resources of moral and psychological pressure are exhausted, and the enemy can still show military resistance, should the appeal of the decision to be taken by arms be used.
- As soon as possible;
- With the lowest cost of lives and material;
- Inflicting the enemy with the least losses. "
- "Generally, in War, the best Policy is to conquer the enemy country intact; destroying it is worse. Capturing the enemy army is better than destroying it. Obtaining a hundred victories through a hundred battles is not the best." ; beating the enemy without the need to fight means the best Strategy. "
- "Managing large staff and materials can become as easy as managing small staff and materials; it's a matter of organization."
- "Generally, whoever chooses the battlefield has advantages; whoever later arrives on the battlefield and engages in combat has disadvantages. That is why sharpened generals lead the enemy to the battlefield they have chosen and reject those chosen by the enemy. No, it will be by offering the enemy some advantages that we will make him act according to our will, but rather by harassing him incessantly. "
- "There are roads that should not be used, troops that should not be attacked, cities that should not be robbed, and regions that should not be disputed."
- "There is nothing more difficult than the art of manoeuvre. The hardest thing about manoeuvring is to make misleading steering the most straightforward and turn that disadvantage into an advantage. So march in an indirect direction, deceiving you with stratagems in other directions. "You have to know how to play a direct and indirect approach."
- "When crossing a river, you should immediately occupy positions at a distance from it."
- "Terrain should be classified according to its nature and operational use as accessible, infiltration-friendly, neutral, enclosed, rugged, and distant."
- "When the troops disband, insubordinate, fail, collapse, disorder, or flee, it is the general's fault. None of these disasters can be attributed to natural causes. When the troops are brave and the officers weak, the result is insubordination: when the officers are brave and the forces vulnerable the result is a failure. "

According to Lenin:

"the establishment of the socialist regime that will suppress all exploitation of man by man and a nation by other nations, which will inevitably contain all possibility of general War. In order to fight for a socialist regime, we will necessarily have to put ourselves in favour of the class struggle within each country, which could lead to a war between the different nations involved in this class struggle. In this way, we cannot avoid the possibility of revolutionary wars, that is, of class struggle wars, directed revolutionary classes, and having a direct and immediate revolutionary goal. "

Several passages of Mao Zedong's Strategy and tactics became known and were the subject of much comment and study in the Western military. Among these we highlight:

"When the enemy moves forward, retreat; when the enemy is high, make him uneasy; when the enemy avoids combat, attack him; when the enemy retreats, pursue him."

"In principle, all displacement of forces must be done covertly and quickly.

- Provoking East while attacking the West;
- appearing simultaneously to the North and South,
- - attacking and disappearing in nocturnal actions, are tactics that should usually be employed to deceive and confuse the enemy.

The ability of commanders to predict tactical attitude changes promptly is not easy to acquire except for those who are able to absorb with the mind and open the experiences of others and their own.

The flexibility of warfare should not be regarded as advance revenue but as a result of actual circumstances. "

"The attack may be changed in defense, and the defense in the attack; the advance may be changed in retreat, and the withdrawal in advance; containment forces may be changed into assault forces, and assault forces shall be changed. containment forces. "

"astute and surprise are the two fundamental principles of the guerrilla.

- All sorts of scheming measures must be taken to mislead the enemy and misjudge him, neutralizing his superiority and denying him any initiative.

- The enemy deluded believes in unreal images. At the same time we must hide our real image of the enemy.

- The eyes and ears of the enemy commanders must be closed.

- Only the weapons of astute are not enough, the enemy commanders must be brought into a state of confusion if possible near despair.

- The moral of the enemy is the highest priority objectives weakening essential before the fighting. "

The principles of Mao Zedong's Strategy, inspired by Sun Tzu's doctrine of indirect action and adapted to Lenin's revolutionary processes, have come under the spell of his long warlike experience - the Chinese Red Army's struggles against Kuomintang forces (Chiang Kai). Chek and the War against the Japanese.

In the XX and XXI century the nuclear change and adapt some theories.

General Beaufre says: "Nuclear deterrence, paralyzing war conflict, leaves a very narrow margin for strategic action - one that is harnessed by Soviet Strategy on the world community: political and economic action, the use of revolutionary movements and even conflict seeking to escape the paralysis imposed by nuclear deterrence. "

French Colonel Guy Doly says: "Nuclear Strategy has pushed Clausewitz's form of direct action to extremes."

As for today's overall Strategy, the best conceptualize is French General André Beaufre himself:

"The total Strategy involves a combination of nuclear deterrence and action. Deterrence is the spring, which cannot but the press, action is the sword, which can ever break and stop.

Deterrence and action are two complementary terms of the Strategy. The concept of action, defined here, encompasses all forms of action; from the most violent to the most insidious.

"It is a total concept that corresponds to the total strategy."

On strategic deterrence, the core of the modern conception of total War into the deterrence neologism, says General Beaufre:

"Nuclear deterrence aims to paralyze the war conflict by imposing on the aggressor the threat of retaliation that would not allow him to survive the aggression."

Bibliography and References – quotes:

ARON, RAYMOND. Penser la Guerre. Clausewitz. Editions Gallimard, Paris, 1976.

BEAUFRE, ANDRÉ. An Introduction to Strategy. New York, Praeger, 1966.

BRADLEY, OMAR. A Soldier's History. New York, Popular Library, 1964.

CASTEX, HUMBERT. Theories Estrategiques. Paris, 1937.

CLAUSEWITZ, KAR L VON. On War. London, 'Penguin 800ks, 1968. CLINE, RAY. World Power Assessment -A Calculus of Strategic Drift.

GLUCKSMANN, ANDRÉ. Le Discours de la Guerre. Editions de l'Herne. Paris, 1967.

GRIFFITH, SAMUEL. Mao Tze Tung on Guerrilla Warfare, New York, Praeger, 1961.

JOMINI, ANTOINE HEN RI. Precis de l'Art de la Guerre. Paris,. 1838.

LENINE, WLADIMIR ULIANOV.Stateand Revolution. Moscow, 1918.

MACHIAVELU, NICOLO. (I Principe. Milano, 1916.

MAHAN, ALFRED T. The influence of the sea power. Boston, Little 8rown, 1949.

MORGENTHAU, HANS. Politics Among Nations, 8orzoI Books, Chicago, 1949.

SUN TZU Art dela Guerre. Paris, Flamarion 1972.

TOYNBEE, ARNO LD. Studv of History, London.